

Parthenon Marbles: The Owners of their Own Unity

Aikaterini Karyofilli

I dedicate this research to the memory of my grandfather, whose love and support continue to inspire me every day.

ABSTRACT

The aim of the argument in this paper is to provide evidence and let history speak for itself. Many governments have tried to solve this dispute unsuccessfully. It has been 193 years since Greece won her independence from the Ottoman Empire and over 200 years since the removal of the sculptures.

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INTRODUCTION

From a temple dedicated to Athena to an armory and later a mosque, the Parthenon has endured centuries of neglect, damage, and destructive alterations, yet stands as a testament to human ingenuity. The Parthenon remains a world symbol of resilience. This paper examines the historical, cultural, and ethical arguments surrounding the Parthenon marbles and argues for their return to Greece.

THE ORIGIN

The Parthenon was built on the Acropolis of Athens between 447 and 438 BC. It was part of a huge construction devised by the Athenian statesman Pericles to celebrate Athen's success in leading the coalition of Greek forces that defeated the invading Persian armies of Darius and Xerxes. Conducted by an extraordinary group of architects (Iktinos, Kallikrates, Mnesikles) and sculptors (such as Pheidias, Alkamenes, Agorakritos). At this stage, it is important to refer to

these works as Greek statues or Parthenon monuments, rather than as the “Elgin Marbles” because the art honors the skill and vision of the original creators, not the individual who removed them. Greece is the center of the world, center of philosophy, art, literature, and intellectual achievement, producing thinkers such as Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle. Athens, with its Acropolis and the Parthenon, symbolized not only political power but also philosophical glory, representing the heights of human creativity and civic organization. Greek art, architecture, and thought continued to inspire Europe and the world, preserving Greece’s reputation as a cradle of Western civilization. Many notable men from wealthy families will visit Greece to educate. You may have heard of this tradition as the Grand Tour, a cultural journey undertaken by young aristocrats, particularly from Britain, France, and Germany, who visited Greece out of a deep interest in ancient ruins, philosophy, and art. In 1700s Greece, although under the Ottoman Empire at the time, many people were influenced to visit its ruins, so travelers needed special permission or letters of introduction to move around safely.

THE SIDE STORY

The Parthenon has suffered extensive damage over the years at the hands of foreigners, but in my opinion, none has been more historically significant than that caused by Thomas Elgin and Philip Hunt, the priest responsible for overseeing the removal of the sculptures. Greece was under Ottoman occupation when in the end of 1799 Thomas Bruce, 7th Earl of Elgin he became British ambassador to the Ottoman Empire (now Constantinople, Turkey). Elgin asked the Ottoman authorities for permission to make casts for his house in Scotland initially. In 1800, he led a team to study the monuments and make mould and drawings for his mansion. Giovanni Battista Lusieri (1755–1821), an Italian painter known for his landscapes, was instrumental as Elgin’s primary artist and representative in Athens. The legacy of Lusieri is complex due to his ethical approach to archaeology: while he aimed to safeguard and document, his involvement in the extraction of cultural heritage raises moral questions today. He not only managed the extraction of the monuments but also exhibited questionable conduct overall. The Turkish officers once ordered the entire team out, accusing them of spying on women, which reflects the controversies and mistrust surrounding their presence in Athens. Elgin used his diplomacy and persuaded the Sultan to allow him to continue to have access to the

Parthenon and to work on his drawings for his house back in Scotland. It was P. Hunt who urged Elgin to use his connections with the Turks to regain access to the Parthenon. The team led by Elgin and Hunt caused damage to the building and sculptures. Taking advantage of this, they collected the monuments from the site and shipped them to England in large crates via the port of Piraeus. Elgin collected a large and heavily damaged collection: 56 blocks of the frieze, 19 pediment statues, 15 metopes, and several architectural elements from the monument. Edward Dodwell, an archaeologist and painter devoted to the study of Mediterranean cultures, also traveled to Greece between 1801 and 1805, he [stumbled](#) see appendix6 a destroyed scene, as [described in his book](#). Lord Byron later wrote his poem “*The Curse of Minerva*” in reference to the cruelty of the events that occurred at the Parthenon, both by the Turks and through Elgin’s actions.

Elgin’s initial objective was to create casts and drawings of the Parthenon sculptures for his house in Scotland, aiming to document the monuments and bring the beauty of Greek art to Britain. Upon arriving in Athens, he realized that removing the original sculptures was feasible and subsequently sought permission from the Ottoman authorities to study the monuments and organize a team of artists and workers. They remove the monuments and transport them because the thought Greece would never overcome her battles. Both Elgin and Giovanni Battista Lusieri, actions presented as acts of preservation from further damage caused by weather, vandalism, or neglect, and enabling future generations to study and appreciate them in better conditions. While preservation was the official justification, it is unclear whether the removal primarily served protective purposes or the personal and elite interests of Elgin and his associates, based on his final decision to sell the marbles to the British Museum after his bankruptcy.

Elgin’s term as British ambassador to the Ottoman empire from 1799 to 1803. Although the Peace of Amiens in 1802 temporarily shifted European diplomacy. While returning home, he was captured by the French and held prisoner until 1806, which ended his diplomatic career. His efforts to remove and transport the Parthenon Marbles cost him a fortune, leaving him deeply in debt and damaging his reputation. Around the same time, he went through a messy divorce, which made him unpopular in high society.

THE UNIQUENESS OF OTHER ARTWORK

The argument that are preserved in London in the best possible way is not true. I will start with the legality of Firman. According to the Trustees statement, *“It was investigated by a Parliamentary Select Committee in 1816 and found to be entirely legal. Following a vote of Parliament, the British Museum was allocated funds to acquire the collection.”* ^{see appendix 12}

When they say it is legal they referred to the Italian Translation ^{figure 1} . The original Ottoman Firman in the worst case is lost; but in reality, it most likely never existed ^{see appendix4}. What exist today is the Italian translation, which the British Museum uses as the only evidence and named it permission. Elgin and his agents could not read Ottoman Turkish fluently to understand and use the Firman, so they had it translated into Italian, which was a common diplomatic language at the time. But according to the Turkish minister of culture Zeynep Boz there was no evidence to prove the peer had been given a permit to strip the fifth century BC monument of the sculptures. She has solid knowledge of what she is talking about; she is a senior Turkish official in a position with access to extensive historical archives and resources. Her assertion that no such document has ever been found and likely never existed is both significant and deserving of deeper investigation and action. ^{See appendix 4.}

Furthermore, cultural minister of Turkey state that *“There were two documents, written in Osmanli, the language of the day, describing what was in the shipments as ceramics and bits of stone, some with images on them but insignificant to the Ottomans,”* she said. *“Both stated he had bought the objects in Athens. There was no reference, whatsoever, to the Parthenon marbles and that’s because Elgin never got permission to remove anything from the site.”* ^{See appendix4.}

Elgin’s legacy is one of contradiction, as he shared a different version of events with each person he encountered. His actions speak louder and make noise that it is not persuasive anymore. Many british governments accepted his Italian translation of the supposed Firman as sufficient evidence. However, in 2025, we possess historical awareness and scholarly tools to recognize that this document lacks legal validity. Both the Trustees and the British Museum continue to base their already fragile argument on an even more fragile document. It has become increasingly evident that they are cornered by the weight of truth, and that the only act capable of restoring their integrity is the permanent, not temporary, return of the Parthenon Marbles. This case stands as unique precisely because its foundation rests upon a historical falsehood. However, the reasons are not only legal but also moral and ethical. There has been a continuous presentation of misleading evidence aimed at retaining ownership of something that was never rightfully owned or granted through legitimate permission.

THE REALITY

The reality is that it is understandable that the British Museum wishes to retain the marbles in its London collection, arguing that they are better preserved there and more accessible to the public. We saw the fragility of their arguments, now I will give you ethical arguments to support that the marbles harmed farther in the British museum. The damage didn't finish there with Elgin actions. It is known to archeologists about the damage caused by unprofessional workers that cleaned the marbles in the 1930s with wire brushes and copper chisels and caused irredeemable changes. ^{See appendix 7&9 and figure 5.}

However, recent events have demonstrated that even within the Museum's archives, such artifacts are not entirely secure, as evidenced by the theft of unique pieces from its collections. ^{See appendix 13.} A potential reunification of the Parthenon Marbles would, in fact, present an optimal opportunity for the Museum to display new works and renew public interest. The institution holds an extensive collection, much of which remains hidden from view. If the Museum's mission is to make art accessible to all, then this moment offers a chance to showcase something new while honoring historical truth and cultural justice. Greece gained independence in 1832 and has, for decades, consistently requested the return of the Parthenon Marbles. The country even constructed a purpose-built museum to house them in the optimal setting at their original cultural and historical context. The marbles are powerful symbols of democracy, yet their continued retention elsewhere contradicts the very values they represent. For the first time in decades, the Parthenon stands entirely free of scaffolding. The removal of scaffolding offers a clear, unobstructed view of the monument, highlighting Greece's commitment to preserving and presenting its cultural heritage. This development underscores Greece's capability to showcase the Parthenon - and its sculptures in their original context, reinforcing the argument for their permanent reunification.

THE CLAIMS AND ARGUMENTS FOR REPATRIATION

Despite repeated UNESCO recommendations, Greece's formal requests, and calls for mediation since 1984, the British Museum has refused to return the Parthenon Sculptures. The British

Museum claims legal ownership under UK law, arguing that Lord Elgin legally purchased the marbles. They also argue that they preserve the sculptures for international audiences, although they have poorly taken care of the artifacts. Greece requested mediation under UNESCO's rules in 2013, but the UK has not actively engaged in a bona fide negotiation to reach a mutually acceptable solution. UNESCO committee expresses "deep concern" and "disappointment" that the UK has not followed its sixteen recommendations for restitution or mediation.

THE WAY FORWARD

The British Museum and the government have characterized this issue as a potential slippery slope; however, it differs from previous cases for the reasons outlined above. This situation presents a significant opportunity for the next administration to adopt a considered, albeit challenging approach. While the measures required may be neither straightforward nor universally popular, addressing them is essential to confronting structural inequalities and ensuring equitable treatment regarding symbols of identity. It is a critical step toward rectifying historical injustices. But there is another reason to do this, a logical one. Let's reconsider the notion that Elgin removed the marbles to protect them from further damage. Imagine your house is damaged and requires renovation. Your neighbor offers to take your family's heirlooms to

preserve them, then decides to display them in his own home. A few years later, he runs out of money and sells your heirlooms to someone else. When you finally rebuild your house and ask for their return, the new owner says, "Sorry, they've been here for a long time, and I bought them legally. Also, they are displayed better in my house because more people pass by my house than yours." You can understand the analogy here; there is no logic in this claim.

And here is my question for you.

What would you do?

I will leave you with a part of the poem of Lord Byron "The course of Minerva".

But basely stole what less barbarians won. So when the Lion quits his fell repast, Next prowls the Wolf, the filthy Jackal last: Flesh, limbs, and blood the former make their own, The last poor brute securely gnaws the bone. Yet still the Gods are just, and crimes are crossed: See here what Elgin won, and what he lost!

Traduzione d'una lettera di S. E. al Signor
Pascia, diretta al giudice, ed anche al revede
d'Atene.

Dopo il solito, vi si fa sapere quante
il vostro amico Simon, S. E. Lordo Segretario
della corte d'Inghilterra per la parte della
felicità, avendo espreso per notizia che la
maggior parte della corte francese, antica di
legge ed in vestigio e libri, le pitture, ed altre
scienze delle filosofie greche, e particolarmente
i Ministri, filosofi, primati, ed altri
individui d'Inghilterra spesso portati alle
pitture rimaste dalle tempi delle G. G. G. G. G.
quali si trovano nelle spingie dell'Arca, ed in
altri libri, abbiamo di tempo in tempo
mandati degli uomini e fatti esplorare l'
antiche fabbriche, e pitture, e che di queste inven-
ti abili edittanti della corte d'Inghilterra
spende desiderosi di vedere l'antiche fabbriche
e le antiche pitture della città d'Atene, e
della vecchia musaglia rimasta dalle G. G. G. G. G.
e che esistono nella parte anteriore del S.
luogo, egli abbia commesso ed ordinato a
cinque Pittori Inglesi, già esistenti nella S.
città, che abbiano a vedere, contemplar, e
anche a dipingere, ^{le pitture} rimaste ab'antico, ed
avendo questa volta espressamente suppleto
avvic

Figure 1 show the Italian translation owned by the British Museum Trustees.

METHODS

The discourse statements were collected from a variety of sources, including library books, government statements, research articles. The study aimed to preserve the author's personal perspective, presenting reasoned statements of opinion. This was achieved through commentary and analogical reasoning, philosophy, drawing inspiration from the Socratic dialectic method to develop and structure the arguments.

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Dr [Emma M. Payne](#) Published online by Cambridge University Press/ 2019. Figure 5.

Figure 2-3-4. University library, Heidelberg University.

Helena Smith *in Athens* 1999/ British damage to Elgin marbles 'irreparable'

Italian translation Owned by the British Museum Trustees.

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APPENDIX

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Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5